

NEW DIRECTIONS IN MODERN LITERATURE, THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF ARTISTIC TRANSLATION

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the new directions in modern literature and the place of literary translation in this process. The article discusses the contribution of literary translation to intercultural relations, interlingual dialogue and literary achievements. The specific features of new literary directions, their significance in cultural and social life, as well as the role of translators in recreating works of art in their own language are highlighted. The article also contains an analytical approach to modern translation methods.

Keywords: Modern literature, literary translation, cultural relations, interlingual dialogue, literary achievement, new directions, translation methods.

Introduction: Along with the development of modern literature, new literary trends and styles have emerged. Literary translation plays an important role in this process. Through translation, the literary heritage of one country comes to life in other languages and cultures, and also gives rise to new literary trends. New trends open the way to discovering new forms and themes of modern literature. Through translation, cultural ties between literatures are strengthened and interlingual dialogue grows. This article analyzes the characteristics of new trends in modern literature, the role of literary translation and its importance.

Modern literature is enriched with new trends and forms in the process of its dynamic development. In each new era, innovations appear in literature in response to social, cultural and scientific changes. Today, postmodernism, socialism, psychological realism and other modern literary trends are adding new dimensions to literary processes. Each of these trends expresses its own worldview, individualism and social changes. These new forms and themes of modern literature undoubtedly increase the importance of literary translation in establishing contacts with other languages and cultures.

Literary translation plays an important role in the international dissemination of literature. Translations create connections not only between transformed forms of language, but also between cultural and aesthetic values. The skill of the translator,

how he correctly reflects the work in reality, how he conveys it to a new audience, significantly affects the literary process. Through literary translation, cultural ties between literatures are strengthened, new trends and styles come closer to each other, and at the same time, contribute to the global development of modern literature.

This article analyzes the new trends taking place in modern literature, their characteristics, as well as the role and significance of literary translation in literature. We will consider how literary translation, as not only the translation of literature, but also a form of intercultural communication, affects the formation of modern literature.

Main part: Modern literature is undergoing various innovations and changes. New trends usually lead to the emergence of new ideas, forms and literary techniques. They mainly include new themes related to individualism, globalization, technological innovations and social changes. At the same time, trends such as postmodernism, fantasy, socialism and ecological literature have also found their place. Modern literature pays great attention to the inner world of the hero, internal conflicts and psychological analysis.

Literary translation is the process of transforming literary works from one language to another. This is not only a change in language, but also the creation of a new culture and literary tradition through the content, style and art of the work. The translator plays an important role in bringing his work to a new audience. In modern translation studies, translation is considered a means of establishing dialogue not only in language, but also in cultures. Thanks to the high skill of translators, works written in other languages come to life in their own language and come to life again.

A number of new methods and techniques have been developed in modern translation studies. For example, through the method of “approximation” (expressive translation), the translator seeks to accurately and completely reflect the content of the original work. Nowadays, with the spread of digital technologies and the Internet, automatic translation tools have also developed. However, for works of art, human translation is still considered the most effective, since it fully expresses the aesthetic and emotional aspects of the original work.

New directions are emerging in modern literature in connection with various social, cultural and scientific changes. In today's literature, postmodernism, ecofiction, psychological realism, feminist literature, socialism and other new trends are increasingly widespread. Postmodernism, for example, abandons traditional literary forms and pays attention to fragmentation, intertextuality, irony. In works written in this direction, events are expressed in a complex, unexpected and multifaceted way.

Ecofiction and ecological literature, on the other hand, raise issues such as the relationship between nature and man, the exploitation of natural resources.

In addition, psychological realism pays great attention to the inner world, emotions, and mental processes of man. Feminist literature, on the other hand, studies the role of women in society and their struggles against injustice. The development of new trends helps literature to spread to a wide circle and express unique social ideas.

Literary translation is a key tool in strengthening the connection of literature with other cultures, in the spread of new trends and forms. A translator is not only a person who changes the language, but also a person who conveys the idea, aesthetic value, and cultural elements expressed in the original work to another audience. Through translation, the literary heritage of one people is reflected in other languages, and at the same time, contacts with other cultures develop.

In modern literature, translation plays a significant role not only in strengthening intercultural ties, but also in ensuring the interaction of new literary trends. For example, modern trends such as postmodernism or ecofiction are spread internationally through translation. Translation is also an important tool for introducing new literary forms and styles into other languages.

Modern translation methods are also changing. In addition to traditional "word-for-word" translation, more "creative" or "free" translation methods are now being used. In these methods, the translator seeks to reflect not only the meaning and idea of the original work, but also its aesthetic and emotional load. In addition, the development of digital technologies and automatic translation tools has accelerated the translation process, but for works of art, a human translator is still important.

In translation, it is necessary to take into account factors such as interlingual differences, intercultural differences, and the specific style of the works. Each translation is unique with its own characteristics, but it remains the main tool for achieving the goal - namely, conveying the content and aesthetics of the original work to another audience.

Conclusion: New trends and literary translation play a significant role in modern literature. Through translation, cultural ties between literatures are further strengthened, new literary forms and techniques are emerging. Translation is not just a process of changing language, but also a process of conveying one culture to another. The development of new literary trends and literary translation helps to discover new forms and themes of modern literature.

The role of new trends and literary translation in modern literature is of incomparable importance. New trends, including postmodernism, ecological literature, feminist and

psychological realism, bring new perspectives, ideas and styles to literature, further enriching the literary process. These trends not only enhance the uniqueness of literature, but also reflect social and cultural changes, helping to disseminate new ideas on a global scale.

Literary translation is an important tool in this process, developing the interaction of literary works with other languages and cultures. Through translation, the literary heritage of a people is spread around the world, and new works are enriched by other cultures, creating opportunities for mutual dialogue. The main thing in translation is to correctly and accurately express the meaning, aesthetic and cultural load of the original work.

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